

THE PROPERTIES AND REQUIREMENTS OF FILAMENT WOUND
CARBON FIBRE REINFORCED PLASTIC RETAINING RINGS,
HOOPS AND CYLINDERS FOR ROTATING ELECTRICAL MACHINES

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Summary

A brief description of the proposed applications is given. These applications require a high degree of integrity over a design life of ~ 25 years. The work described here concerns the static and tension/tension fatigue properties of small rings of HT-S carbon fibre reinforced epoxy resin loaded in the hoop direction at room temperature and 100°C . It is part of a large on-going programme with the direct objective of seeing through the full scale application of much larger rings, hoops and cylinders.

Both hoop and double 70° angle wound rings were tested. Fatigue limits corresponding to $\sim 10^7$ cycles, were found to occur close to or below the lower bound of the static strength scatterband. Mean stress, stress amplitude and temperature has little effect on the fatigue limit of the hoop wound rings. In contrast a high mean stress/large stress amplitude reduces the fatigue life in the double 70° angle wound rings at stresses above the fatigue limit; when the stress amplitude is sufficiently high, increasing the temperature to 100°C reduces the fatigue life further. Results of residual strength measurements show that pre-fatiguing may be beneficial in some cases.

No effect of ring size was observed and a few results on larger rings and cylinders were found to fit into the pattern of results established for the smaller rings tested here.

Introduction

In the power generation industry consideration is being given to the use of large hoops and cylinders of composite materials for certain critical components requiring high integrity over long periods of time (~ 25 years) and operating at elevated temperatures ($\sim 100^\circ\text{C}$). Indeed it appears that these materials and the associated fibre hoop technology may well be essential in the designs envisaged for two new types of generator, namely the slotless and rotating armature. The function of these critical components is the containment of electrical windings during machine rotation. With conventional generators an alternative to high strength steel for the end-winding retaining rings (end-bells) may be desirable. Composite materials offer a number of advantages both as replacement material and for use in very large new generators, where the size of end-ring is typically 1.3m outer diameter, 0.1m wall thickness, and 0.8 m in length. Carbon fibre reinforced plastic is particularly attractive because of its high specific strength and modulus which can offer significant advantages for rotating electrical machines. However, there is little information on the long term properties of this material at high temperatures and effects of specimen size are unknown. Of particular concern is the stop/start operation of these machines which gives rise to large amplitude fatigue cycles, and there is in addition small load variations during continuous operation which superimposes fatigue cycles on a high mean stress level.

As a first step to obtaining some of the required information tension/tension fatigue tests have been performed on small, thin rings of HT-S carbon fibre reinforced epoxy resin loaded in the hoop direction. It is of course impractical to test large numbers of full-size rings, hoops and cylinders, although hydraulic pressure and spin tests on larger rings and cylinders are being performed. The present intention is to conduct spinning trials on the full size components, if the preliminary results prove satisfactory.

The proposed winding pattern for these rings is either a simple hoop wind or a hoop wind plus a double angle wind.

Experimental

Ring specimens were used for all tests and were manufactured by filament winding carbon fibre tow in an epoxy resin matrix. Courtauld's HT-S carbon fibre was used, a tow consisting of $\sim 10,000$ continuous filaments each $\sim 7\mu$ diameter. The load on the tow during winding was 5lb f. Typical properties of the fibre were: ultimate tensile strength 2.94GN/m^2 , tension modulus $220\text{-}250\text{GN/m}^2$. The resin system consisted of Ciba-Geigy epoxy resin MY750, Shell Hardener Epicure NMA, and Ciba-Geigy Accelerator DYO62 (benzylidimethyl amine) which were mixed in the proportions 100/90/0.5 and used immediately. The glass transition temperature of the resin system was $\sim 150^\circ\text{C}$. Throughout the winding period the resin system was maintained at $50^\circ\text{C} + 5^\circ\text{C}$ so that the viscosity was about 2 to 3 poises. Ring specimens were chosen because it is most important in evaluating composite materials to use specimens of the same form as the proposed application. Moreover, the rings were manufactured by the same filament winding process used to make large hoops and cylinders. The size of rings was chosen such that the diameter/thickness ratio was large as would be the case for most of the proposed applications.

Tubes were wound on a 69mm diameter steel mandrel having a taper 1mm/m, using a continuous in-line vacuum impregnating plant and a digital controlled filament winding machine to ensure accurate fibre array. After completion of filament winding, the 600mm long tubes were gelled at 70°C whilst still rotating and then step-cured up to 180°C where they were held for 24 hours. They were then ground on the outside to the required dimensions before removal from the mandrel. The tubes were then usually cut up into 25.4mm

wide rings with a diamond slitting wheel, although smaller width rings were also prepared. The thickness of the rings varied from $\sim 0.76\text{mm}$ to $\sim 1.27\text{mm}$.

Two winding patterns were studied, a hoop wind and a double helix 70° angle wind. Three composite structures were manufactured in hoop wound form, 55%, 45% and 35% fibre volume, the first two structures containing no voids, the third structure containing 1.7% voids which were introduced by deliberately winding at high speed thus giving poor impregnation.

The rings were fatigued in tension/tension, mostly in a servo-hydraulic machine at a frequency of 20-26Hz, and under load control. Testing under displacement control had no measurable effect on the fatigue behaviour. Some tests were also carried out in a Schenck machine at similar frequencies. In addition some low frequency tests were performed in an Instron machine and some high frequency tests in an Amsler machine. Frequency had little effect on the results reported here. Tests at 100°C were performed using an electrically heated air furnace around the specimen and grips. Static properties were determined in the same machines used for the fatigue tests.

Loads were applied through two back to back split steel D's which fitted closely inside the ring specimens and were located by standard pins in 1" CKS grips. To minimise friction between the composite ring and the D's a thin layer of PTFE was baked onto the curved surface of both D's. This should allow the whole of the ring circumference to enter into the total strain on the rings. It is realised that this method of loading is not completely satisfactory in that the loading on the ring is not entirely uniform. However, the loading on a ring in service is not expected to be uniform either, and it is considered that the results of these tests may be regarded as minimum properties obtainable by more uniformly loading the rings.

Experimental Results

Results of the fatigue tests on hoop wound rings are shown in Fig. 1. The data is plotted as maximum fatigue stress versus number of fatigue cycles. Most of the points correspond to a mean stress of 460MN/m^2 . For the composites containing 55% and 45% fibre volume with no voids there is a critical stress $\sim 800\text{MN/m}^2$ below which no fatigue failure is observed, at least up to $\sim 10^7$ cycles. This critical stress level is reduced to $\sim 700\text{MN/m}^2$ for the composite containing 35% fibre volume and 1.7% voids. Testing at other mean stresses had no significant effect on the results and tests at 100°C were not significantly different to those at room temperature. Where the maximum stress was close to the lower bound of the static strength scatter band, specimens sometimes broke on the first cycle.

Also shown in Fig. 1 are the static strength scatter bands for the three hoop wound composites. Results at 100°C were not significantly different to those at room temperature.

Fig. 2 shows the results of fatigue tests on the double 70° angle wound rings, containing 50% fibre volume with no voids. The mean stress value 230MN/m^2 was such as to represent the severest stress amplitude condition at $\sim 10^4$ cycles, corresponding to the number of stop/start cycles in a typical design life of ~ 25 years. The mean stress value 370MN/m^2 was sufficiently close to the fatigue limit to simulate the high frequency small stress amplitude load oscillations which may occur during continuous machine operation. Unlike the hoop wound rings, a high mean stress/large stress amplitude causes fatigue failure to occur after a smaller number of fatigue cycles at stresses above the fatigue limit. Tests at 100°C showed that rings fatigued at a sufficiently large stress amplitude failed after fewer fatigue cycles than at room temperature. As with the hoop wound rings, where the maximum stress was close to the lower bound of the static strength scatter band, specimens some-

FIG. 1 EFFECT OF COMPOSITE STRUCTURE ON STATIC AND FATIGUE PROPERTIES OF HOOP WOUND RINGS. ALL THE RINGS WERE LOADED IN TENSION. THE POINTS MARKED 'T' WERE FATIGUED AT 100°C, AND THE UNMARKED POINTS AT ROOM TEMPERATURE. NO EFFECT OF TEMPERATURE WAS OBSERVED ON STATIC PROPERTIES WITHIN THE SCATTER BANDS SHOWN

times broke in the first cycle. At the high mean stress level at 100°C specimens either failed on the first cycle or were able to sustain a large number of cycles without failure. The static strength scatterband contains results at both room temperature and 100°C, there being no significant difference.

Some fatigue tests were stopped and the residual strength measured. Fig. 3 shows that no deleterious effects were observed even when the fatigue stress was close to the fatigue limit. This was true for all rings at both temperatures.

Fracture surfaces were examined in the scanning electron microscope. No difference was detected between tensile and fatigue fracture surfaces. The hoop wind fracture surface was irregular and brush-like in appearance; some longitudinal splitting around the circumference was observed in addition to fibre fracture but the main crack front was perpendicular to the load line. The 70° angle wind fracture surface was also irregular and some delamination between layers was observed; the fracture line was saw-tooth in appearance, the crack following the winding pattern, but the general crack direction was again perpendicular to the load line.

FIG. 2 EFFECT OF MEAN STRESS ON FATIGUE PROPERTIES OF DOUBLE 70° ANGLE WOUND RINGS (~ 50 VOLUME PERCENT FIBRE) AT 100°C AND ROOM TEMPERATURE. ALL THE RINGS WERE LOADED IN TENSION. NO EFFECT OF TEMPERATURE WAS OBSERVED ON STATIC PROPERTIES WITHIN THE SCATTER BAND SHOWN

Discussion

The critical maximum fatigue stress level of $\sim 800\text{MN/m}^2$, observed for the 45/55% fibre volume hoop wound rings, below which no fatigue failure occurs, agrees well with that established for flat, unidirectional carbon fibre reinforced plastic composites loaded along the fibre direction (1,2) and tested at room temperature. No significant differences were detected with hoop wound rings tested at 100°C.

Reducing the fibre volume to 35% and introducing 1.7% voids resulted in a lower critical maximum fatigue stress level, but the effect on the static properties was much more marked (Fig. 1). The more marked effect on static properties compared to the critical maximum fatigue stress level is also seen in results obtained in composites with different types of fibre (1,2).

The results are important for an engineer designing against tension/tension fatigue because the critical maximum fatigue stress is a relatively stable parameter even though a large scatter may be observed in static strength properties. Moreover, it appears that some change in composite structure may be tolerated and that choice of fibre type is not too restricted by fatigue considerations.

Unlike the hoop wound rings the matrix in the double 70° angle wound rings is subject to appreciable shear strain as well as normal strain. Moreover, fibre cross-overs provide points of stress and strain concentration

FIG. 3 EFFECT OF PRE-FATIGUING ON THE RESIDUAL STRENGTH OF HOOP AND DOUBLE 70° ANGLE WOUND RINGS. ALL THE RINGS WERE LOADED IN TENSION. THE POINTS MARKED 'T' WERE FATIGUED AT 100°C AND THE UNMARKED POINTS AT ROOM TEMPERATURE. 'R' IS THE RESIDUAL STRENGTH

throughout the rings. For these reasons the matrix will be subject to severe deformation and it is thought that this gives rise to the effects of mean stress, stress amplitude and temperature observed with the angle wound rings. It is believed that cracks can form in the matrix when the stress amplitude is greater than some minimum value, and that the cracks are able to spread more readily under a high mean stress. Where the maximum stress is close to the region of the lower bound of the static strength scatterband fibre fracture becomes important and specimens can sometimes break on the first cycle. However, where fatigue can occur specimens under a high mean stress can sometimes sustain a large number of cycles because the matrix is unable to crack immediately, and this was always found to occur at 100°C. Specimens under a low mean stress and large stress amplitude always broke after fewer cycles at 100°C than at room temperature. It seems that in addition to the normal minimum stress amplitude required for fatigue failure there is also a larger stress amplitude above which increasing temperature causes a marked reduction in the cycles to failure. Clearly the introduction of angle winding will limit the fatigue performance of a hoop wound ring. However, the limitation will be less severe than observed here if the angle wind can be incorporated such that ground and cut surfaces are avoided (3).

Pre-fatiguing causes no marked reduction in residual strength (Fig. 3) for either the hoop or double 70° angle wound rings. Indeed pre-fatiguing for angle wound rings at 100°C can be regarded as beneficial.

Fatigue life prediction is very difficult in the material tested here. It is quite unlike glass fibre reinforced plastic for example, where the properties deteriorate throughout the fatiguing process resulting in a decrease in modulus and residual strength. No such decrease was observed in the present work and the use of cumulative damage rules does not seem applicable. Nonetheless some form of fatigue life prediction coupled with an acceptable and meaningful inspection criterion will have to be established before the material can be allowed into service for the applications envisaged here.

It is likely that hoop winding will be the main form of construction and some static strength properties of large hoop wound rings are given in the Table. All the rings contained 55 volume percent fibre with no voids, and were tested at room temperature, except the one noted at 100°C. Included in the Table are results from rings made with HM-S fibre since the smaller strains may be preferred for some of these applications. It has also been shown that a large high modulus carbon fibre hoop wound ring was able to survive 10⁵ cycles when fatigued in the range 0 to 930MN/m², and a large high strength carbon fibre angle wound cylinder survived 2,770 cycles when fatigued in the range 0 to 465MN/m². These results are in good agreement with those obtained with small rings.

TABLE

Fibre & Wind	Ring Internal Diameter mm	Ring Width mm	Ring Thickness mm	Fracture Stress MN/m ²	Test Details
HT-S Hoop	69.0	25.0	1.5	1,120	NOL Ring Monotonic Test
HT-S Hoop	167.0	31.0	2.4	1,240	Pressure Monotonic Test
HT-S Hoop	167.0	31.0	2.4	1,370	Pressure Monotonic Test
HM-S Hoop	457.2	30.5	17.8	1,110	Pressure Monotonic Test
HM-S Hoop	457.2	30.5	17.8	930	Pressure Monotonic Test Pre-fatigued, to 10 ⁵ cycles 0/266MN/m ²
HM-S Hoop	457.2	30.5	17.8	1,160	Pressure Monotonic Test 100°C

It is concluded that larger rings and hoops do not show reduced properties and it seems generally that rather better properties are obtained. The indications are that carbon fibre reinforced plastic in the form of large rings, hoops, and cylinders is suitable as containment material for large electrical machines. However, consideration will have to be given to the effect of notches, which may introduce a size effect in thick rings, and to the problem of fitting these components.

Conclusions

1. In hoop wound rings fatigued in tension/tension in the hoop direction there is a critical maximum stress level below which no fatigue failure is observed, at least up to ~10⁷ cycles. This critical stress level occurs in the region of the lower bound of the static strength scatter-band, well below the maximum static strength. Mean stress and temperature (room temperature and 100°C) have little effect on this critical stress level. Changes in fibre volume and void content have far more

effect on static strength properties than on the fatigue critical stress level.

2. In double 70° angle wound rings fatigued in tension/tension in the hoop direction fatigue life decreases as the maximum stress increases above the fatigue limit at both room temperature and 100°C. When the stress amplitude is sufficiently high increasing the temperature to 100°C reduces the fatigue life further.
3. Pre-fatiguing both hoop and double 70° angle wound rings at room temperature and 100°C causes no marked reduction in the residual strength at room temperature. Pre-fatiguing double 70° angle wound rings at 100°C appears to be beneficial.
4. No effect of ring size was observed and a few results on larger rings and cylinders were found to fit into the pattern of results established for the smaller rings tested here.

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